

Eagle-Tripati Laboratories
Guide for clumped isotope data quality assessment, including measurement flagging
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- **Definitions:**

- Data quality assessment: the process of assessing if data are reproducible, including identifying if there were statistical outliers that may arise due to incomplete sample digestion, voltage fluctuations, exchange with water, carousel not advancing properly, or other processes relating to sample reaction, purification, and measurement, etc., resulting in an erroneous measurement or non-representative value
- Flagging: identifying a statistical outlier that you hypothesize is due to an erroneous measurement or is not representative of the sample, that you think should not be included in calculations.
 - You need ≥ 3 replicates to begin flagging.
- Outlier: an observation that statistically lies an abnormal distance from other values in a random sample from a population.
- Exclusion: removal of an analysis from the population.
 - Before excluding a replicate, talk to Aradhna/Rob and Ben about why it's being excluded – there may be a solution to the issue.
 - You must include detailed notes on the justification in both the run log and in Easotope, after discussion with Aradhna/Rob and Ben
- Standard deviation: a measure of the amount of variation or dispersion of a set of values. A low standard deviation indicates that the values tend to be close to the mean (also called the expected value) of the set, while a high standard deviation indicates that the values are spread out over a wider range.

$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum |x - \mu|^2}{N}}$ where x is the replicate value, μ is the population mean, and N is the number of replicates.

- Standard error: SD/\sqrt{N}
- Correction interval: a time period when the instrument was running with similar conditions and has well-characterized standard variability.
 - New correction intervals are identified when there is a shift in raw values (can be caused by instrument contamination), instrument repairs (e.g., source cleaning, filament change), or other issues (e.g., power outage).

- **Directions:**

- **Assess instrument behavior:** Do an initial quality check on every run log where you have samples that were analyzed. Make sure that you check/note in the run log if there were samples missed, problems with instrument behavior, standards that did not run well. Observations should be noted in both the instrument run log and in Easotope. Talk with Ben and the people who ran the same day/the day before/after.
- **Initial quality check:** Do an initial quality check on your data in Easotope: Show all columns, export/download the standard and sample data. Sort in excel by date to check

each sample in the run log. Check the acid temperature column (if on CDES server), mineralogy, First MZ 44 sample (to check transfer). Sort by the standard error on the raw 47 - this is a really good indicator of if you have a spurious cycle, or if maybe an extra acquisition was pulled into there. It is easier to correct during this step, pre-exporting.

- **Quality assessment:** Then download both the project spreadsheet and standard spreadsheet in Easotope at the same time. This ensures you have the standard data used to calculate your final values. Note: an initial assessment is preliminary. Best to wait **3 days**, and eventually allow a minimum of **7 days** between your last replicate analysis and when you do a final download of your spreadsheets. This allows time for standards to be run after your samples so the standardization is robust.

- Easotope → Screens → Table Overview → select your project → Load Table → select Export from both the top (samples) AND bottom (standards) tables

- Flaggging:
 - Create a column labeled “Notes” in your spreadsheets. In this column, write down notes regarding why a replicate was flagged.
 - Calculate the replicate mean, standard deviation, and standard error for each sample replicate pool (as long as you have at least 3 replicates) for d13C, d18O, D47, and D48.
 - Values that are ≥ 3 SD from the mean should be flagged (Meckler et al., 2014; Lucarelli et al., 2022)
 - You may also use an outlier test for each sample replicate pool, such as a Grubb’s test (you can perform these tests in PRISM, R, etc)
 - Examine the D47 and D48 ETF slope and nonlinearity slope columns.
 - D47 ETF slope should be $\sim 1.0-1.2$.
 - D47 nonlinearity slope should be very small, $\sim -0.01-0.0001$.
 - D48 ETF slope should be $\sim 1-1.5$, but can vary between $\sim 0.5-2.1$.
 - D48 nonlinearity slope should be very small, $\sim -0.01-0.001$.
 - Values outside of these limits should be flagged.
 - Examine the error in raw values
 - d18O VPDB (Raw) SD should be $\sim \leq 0.12$
 - d47 WG (Raw) SD should be $\sim \leq 0.17$
 - d48 WG (Raw) SD should be $\sim \leq 0.30$

- Values outside of these limits should be flagged.
- Other columns labelled “Raw” can be examined in a similar way, looking for replicates with values that are significantly higher than other replicates
 - Replicates with high SDs for raw values may have an issue on a “cycle by cycle” level, meaning one cycle during the measurement had an error. You can speak with Ben regarding how to disable a cycle. **Do not disable a cycle without approval from Ben or Aradhna/Rob.**
- If you are **certain** that your samples should have formed at Earth surface temperatures and that they do not have kinetic isotope effects, mixing effects, diagenetic effects, etc., that could be affecting the isotopic values:
 - Replicates with D47-reconstructed temperatures that are >40 C or <0 C can be flagged
 - Replicates with D47 CDES (Final) values >0.67 or <0.42 can be flagged
- When you have finished flagging your replicates, discuss the flagged values with Ben and/or Aradhna/Rob. If all options to recover a usable value fail (e.g., from poor instrument performance or contamination), then you may exclude the replicate (all associated values) from your dataset. It is recommended to “cut” the replicate from your sample spreadsheet and “paste” the replicate into a spreadsheet labelled “Excluded values for project X”. You need to keep track of all excluded values.
- Other notes:
 - Your standard spreadsheet should be examined in the same way as your sample spreadsheet, with the exception of calculating D47-temperatures.
 - If you find standard replicates with values that are outliers, discuss options with Ben and/or Aradhna/Rob. **Please do not disable any standard replicates in Easotope.** Note in the sample run log.
 - Make sure to take notes discussing how/why your exclusions were performed. Note in the sample run log and in Easotope. You will have to report this when you publish your work.